

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

ADVERSE SOILS TOLERANCE

Selecting for alkali soils

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Severely deteriorated alkali soils of the Indo-gangetic plain, are characterized by high pH (usually more than 9.0), sodicity (exchangeable sodium percentage often exceeding 30), calcium carbonate precipitation, Zn deficiency, and poor physical properties. Groundwater is good.

Progress toward combining superior tolerance with good yield potential is slow, largely because of nonavailability of reliable and efficient selection criteria. Selecting directly for grain yield under edaphic stress is limited by low heritability of observed variation and failure to distinguish between yield potential and capacity to cope with specific stress factors.

For indirect selection for yield ability under alkali soil conditions, 30 rice varieties were studied in specially designed 3 m × 3 m × 1 m test plots with 2 alkali soil grades (pH 9.3 and 9.6) and in nonstress productive soil over 3 seasons. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. N, P, K, and Zn were applied at 150, 26, 33, and 9 kg/ha. Irrigation followed a specified schedule.

Heritability of 12 characteristics of rice varieties grown in alkali (sodic) soils, and their correlation with grain yield and alkali stress resistance index.^a Karnal, India.

Characteristic	Heritability	Correlation	
		Grain yield	Alkali stress resistance index
Seed germination percentage	30.64	0.14	0.09
Germination rate index	39.81	0.19	0.27
Seedling growth rate	36.25	0.39	0.41
Foliar damage score	45.07	0.37	0.44
Plant height	38.54	0.28	0.29
Vegetative growth rate index	49.86	0.46	0.48
Biomass yield	64.91	0.67	0.71
Panicle-bearing tillers/plot	29.10	0.30	0.29
Grains/plant (no.)	37.29	0.38	0.32
1000-grain weight	35.47	0.41	0.37
Panicle weight	81.10	0.73	0.79
Harvest index	21.17	0.13	0.11

^an = 720 (30 varieties, 2 alkali soils, 4 replications, 3 yr). 'r' value required for 0.01 level of significance = 0.25.

Because grain yield corresponds to product of biomass or total dry matter production (growth rate × growth duration) and harvest index, correlations of 12 characteristics with grain yield under stress conditions *per se* as well as with the "stress resistance index" (average grain yield under stress in relation to corresponding controls taken as one) were computed and variances and heritability of parameters estimated (see table).

Total biomass and panicle weight correlated highly with grain yield under alkali soil conditions as well as with the stress resistance index. A simultaneous

consideration of correlation coefficients and heritability estimates of different traits showed that indirect selection for grain yield in alkali soils via panicle weight and biological yield (cf. harvest index in case of high productivity environment) was likely to be effective.

The product of a variety's yield response index (computed by dividing the particular variety's grain yield by overall mean yield of all varieties under all stress environments) and its stress resistance index provided a more useful index for measuring varietal ratings (rankings) than either index alone. *S*

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DEEP WATER

A simple technique for measuring internode elongation of deep water rice

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There are two problems in measuring elongation ability of deep water and floating rice.

Measurement is best some 70 d after broadcast seeding, but this requires fairly deep tanks. But for savings in time and water, most tests are carried out at 30 d after seeding, and in water no more than 100-150 cm deep.

In genetics work, it is essential to do progeny tests on all individuals, including those found unable to

elongate. Plants in the latter category, however, are destroyed in all current tests.

We tested a new approach to elongation testing by forcing test plants in a horizontal position, except for their upper parts.

Six varieties were selected: TCA4, TCA177 (floating rice), Janki (deep

water rice, submergence tolerant), IR11141-6-1-4 (modern deep water rice variety, elongation ability), IR42 (MV rice), and Lal Dhan (tall traditional rice).

Five 8-wk-old plants of each variety were grown in small (5- × 5-cm) plastic pots. Only the main tillers were maintained. Plants were placed horizontally in trays, and a weight was applied at the uppermost node and a support ventrally under this node (see figure), to stimulate vertical growth of the upper portion of the plant.

Four days after treatment, TCA4, TCA177, Janki, and IR11141-6-1-4 showed excellent kneeling, while IR42 and Lal Dhan were not able to knee, possibly because of the absence of sufficiently developed internodes.

Plants were then submerged for 6 d, initially keeping the leaves partly above the water. IR42 and Lal Dhan had no internode elongation at all, but the other varieties developed two internodes while partially submerged, with the first internode being smaller. TCA4 had the

Sketch of horizontally placed plant, with top part being forced to grow vertically.

longest average total internode elongation of 34.6 cm/plant, followed by TCA177 (32.6 cm). Janki elongated 12.4 cm and IR11141-6-1-4 had 10.4 cm total elongated internodes.

This method has the following advantages: it minimizes the need for

deep flooding to induce elongation, it does not destroy any entry, and it allows scoring (in cm internode length) on a continuous scale between no elongation and very good elongation.

We will evaluate this method for use in elongation genetics work. *ℵ*

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization HYBRID RICE

Relation of cross seed set and fertility in rice hybrids

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While breeding for cold tolerance at IRRI, crosses were made with nine japonica and eight indica (including two indica-type derivatives of indica/japonica crosses) cold-tolerant female parents from diverse sources, and six improved plant type, high yielding indica IRRI lines as pollen parents. The cross seeds per panicle and per cross were recorded. Varying degrees of sterility were indicated by seed set of the cross combinations. We tried to find out if the seed set in 102

cross combinations was related to the fertility of the F_1 hybrids.

A total of 299,539 spikelets were emasculated in Feb-Apr 1984 and pollinated using 6 pollinators: 50,864 with IR8866, 48,001 with IR8455-K2, 48,666 with IR15889, 51,439 with IR7167, 48,253 with IR29506, and 52,316 with IR9202. Total seed set was 165,000.

To determine F_1 fertility, 102 hybrids were grown in different environments: in the experimental field, in pots in the greenhouse and in the concrete bed at IRRI, and at CES, Chuncheon, in the 1984 rice growing season. Twenty seedlings of each F_1 were transplanted in single-plant hills, with 25 cm between plants and rows in the field and in the concrete bed, and 5 seedlings in the pots. The main culm panicle of each plant was harvested and placed in a

separate envelope shortly before full maturity to avoid shattering. Spikelet fertility was measured in one panicle per plant, for a maximum of 15 F_1 plants/hybrid combination in Chuncheon, 10 plants in the field and the concrete bed, and 5 plants in pots at IRRI.

The table summarizes the seed set and F_1 fertility data by common indica male parent. The overall mean cross seed set ranged from 53.3% in IR7167 array to 58.8% in IR29506 array with an overall mean of 55.8%. Samgangbyeon and K332 represented the extremes in cross seed set with means of 78.4% and 39.6% among the female parents. Samgangbyeon was followed by Silewah, ARC6000, Shoa-Nan-Tsan, Suweon 287, all indica types. The highest mean F_1 fertility was also recorded in Samgangbyeon (80.2%),